

Business Communication

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We need to understand that the ability to communicate correctly and effectively is the skill on which a good portion of our success depends. Communication skills are prerequisite to personal, academic and professional success. Communication plays a vital role in business organisations. Efficient communication prevents possible failure situations and events by feeding the information forward and help in making a proper business proposal. Business communication today has undergone a massive change due to the highly competitive business environment and different working conditions. Managing a business implies coordinating activities of diverse groups like owners, employees, suppliers, customers etc. Effective communication is what holds it all together. It results in building trust and teamwork amongst all stakeholders.

This book can be useful for the person who is pursuing MBA and also beneficial to them who are working in a corporate company and want to enhance their position. Moreover, it can also be helpful for an enthusiast doing a simple graduation or post graduation degree. It does not only depict certain rules about communication rather takes all things together like, resume writing, group discussion, business mailing and many more. It covers multiple things and presents them before us in one book. There lies the acceptability of this book across the different stakeholders of our society.

There are total 15 chapters in this book. As a reader, you will start with understanding business communication, writing business messages and documents, developing oral communications skills for business and you might move toward understanding specific communication needs. So, it is designed in a way that students or the readers will find it pretty easy to access and understand step by step. The book is designed in a way to provide the reader with adequate exposure to the various form and practices of business communication, primarily

focusing on the communication needs of management students. However, at the same time, it will serve to best to working professionals as well who want to learn communication in depth. Topics related to technology, legal and ethical aspects of business, employment interview, global and cross-cultural communication have also been incorporated to this book along with the basic concepts. Overall, as a reference resource for teachers and learners this is a helpful book.

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